

Rapid ^{210}Pb assay for monitoring the purification of archaeological lead for the RES-NOVA experiment

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An archaeological lead based detector

The RES-NOVA experiment

- Detection of Supernovae neutrinos (all flavours) [1]
- Detection of Dark Matter candidates (WIMPs) [2]
- Interaction channel: Coherent Elastic Neutrino Nucleus Scattering [3]
- Cryogenic detector with archaeological lead PbWO_4 crystals

Total Frames Shields
Crystals Tiles External

Main background: ^{210}Pb in PbWO_4 crystals Archaeological lead grants highest radiopurity! [4]

Measure optimization and results

Quenching effects Detector linearity

Detection efficiency ROIs definition

Detection limits for 0.8 g of archaeological lead

Wallac Quantulus 1220 for Liquid Scintillation (LS) detection

- 20 ml volume samples: 12 ml LS + 8 ml digested lead
- Detection of the whole ^{210}Pb decay chain
- Pulse Shape Analysis (PSA) for α/β particle discrimination

Optimal technique for monitoring ^{210}Pb contaminations between chemical purification processes of archaeo-lead

References

- [1] Pattavina, Luca, Nahuel Ferreiro Iachellini, and Irene Tamborra. "Neutrino observatory based on archaeological lead." *Physical Review D* 102.6 (2020): 063001.
- [2] RES-NOVA Coll. "New dark matter direct search based on archaeological Pb", *Phys.Rev.D* 111 (2025) 10, 103050
- [3] Akimov, D., et al. "Observation of coherent elastic neutrino-nucleus scattering." *Science* 357.6356 (2017): 1123-1126.
- [4] Pattavina, L., et al. "Radiopurity of an archaeological Roman lead cryogenic detector." *The European Physical Journal A* 55.8 (2019): 127.

FAST TECHNIQUE:

sensitivity < 300 mBq/kg in 1 week
sensitivity < 100 mBq/kg in 42 days